

THE CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF ASSESSMENT AND EVALUATION IN LANGUAGE TEXTBOOKS FOR NON-PHILOLOGICAL FIELDS

Muxamedova Muhlisa Avazjon qizi

PhD student at Chirchik state pedagogical university

boburmuhlisa@gmail.com

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Abstract

In domains other than philology, assessment and evaluation are crucial elements of language learning. Nevertheless, language textbooks for these subjects frequently employ assessment and evaluation techniques that are insufficient to satisfy the demands of both teachers and students. The assessment and evaluation techniques employed in language textbooks for non-philological subjects are critically examined in this article, which also highlights their shortcomings and offers substitute strategies that may enhance language acquisition in these domains.

Key words: Assessment, Evaluation Language, Non-philological fields, Authenticity, Reliability, Validity, Student learning and development

Introduction

The increased awareness of the value of language proficiency in professional contexts has contributed to the rise in popularity of language textbooks for non-philological professions. Students who want to work in fields like business, engineering, or medical, among others, are becoming more conscious of how important it is to speak English well in order to be successful in their chosen fields.

But these textbooks' methods of assessment and evaluation frequently don't suit the demands of students studying these subjects. Although vocabulary development and grammatical correctness are crucial for language learners, they are not the sole abilities required for success in the workplace. The capacity to communicate well in a range of settings, including as meetings, presentations, and written reports, is actually highly valued by many companies and professionals in non-philological professions.

Language textbooks for non-philological subjects may have a limited and constrained perspective on language learning because of their emphasis on vocabulary acquisition and grammatical correctness. Students may find it difficult to use their language abilities in authentic situations and may believe they are not sufficiently equipped for the demands of their career. In industries like business and health, where successful communication is essential, this can

be especially troublesome. The practical use of language in everyday situations should be given more attention in language textbooks for non-philological subjects in order to solve this problem. More scenario-based exercises and activities that mimic the kinds of communication tasks students would face in the workplace could be used to achieve this. It might also entail giving students chances to practice their language abilities in more dynamic and real-world contexts, including role-plays or group conversations.

METHODOLOGY

The study on assessment and evaluation in language textbooks for non-philological subjects is reviewed in this article. The review focuses on the shortcomings of the existing methods of assessment and evaluation, such as their lack of validity, authenticity, and reliability. Alternative methods of assessment and evaluation, including project-based assessment, peer assessment, and self-assessment, are also covered in the article.

RESULTS

Current assessment and evaluation techniques in language textbooks for non-philological disciplines have a number of drawbacks, according to a review of the literature. The following limitations are analyzed:

Lack of authenticity: Language textbooks for non-philological subjects frequently employ assessment and evaluation techniques that are not grounded in real-world situations, rendering them unrelated to students' intended vocations. This may cause a gap between the language proficiency that students acquire in the classroom and that which they require to be successful in their line of work. A student might learn how to write a formal letter in a textbook, for instance, but might not get the chance to practice writing one in a real-world setting.

Lack of reliability: One of the primary issues with unreliable assessment methods is that they can lead to a lack of confidence in students' abilities. When students are uncertain about how they will be assessed, they may feel anxious and uncertain about their performance, which can negatively impact their motivation and engagement with the learning material. Furthermore, unreliable assessment methods can also perpetuate a culture of insecurity and doubt among students. When students are consistently faced with unpredictable and inconsistent assessment results, they may begin to question their own abilities and wonder if they are truly capable of meeting the demands of the course. The creation of trustworthy assessment and evaluation techniques that appropriately represent students' language proficiency should be given top

priority in language textbooks for non-philological subjects in order to solve this problem. This can be accomplished by using a range of evaluation techniques and instruments that give students a comprehensive picture of their performance and development. For instance, more realistic and performance-based tests that mimic language use in everyday situations should be included in language textbooks. Writing a business letter, making a presentation, or taking part in a role-playing conversation are a few examples of these kinds of assignments. Students can exhibit their language proficiency in a more genuine and meaningful way and get pertinent, useful feedback by using these kinds of tests.

Lack of validity: One drawback of improper evaluation techniques is that they may cause students' language proficiency to be misrepresented. Students may be unjustly punished or rewarded when assessment techniques are not in line with the linguistic skills and abilities they have acquired. Students may become less confident as a result of this since they may believe that their efforts and hard work are not appreciated. Additionally, a culture of superficiality and shallow evaluation can be sustained by unreliable assessment techniques. When students are evaluated based on limited or fabricated standards, they could prioritize fulfilling such standards above gaining a thorough comprehension of the language and its applications. The creation of reliable and authentic assessment and evaluation techniques that fairly represent students' language proficiency should be given top priority in language textbooks for non-philological subjects in order to solve this problem. This can be accomplished by using a range of evaluation techniques and instruments that give students a comprehensive picture of their performance and development. For instance, more realistic and performance-based tests that mimic language use in everyday situations should be included in language textbooks. Writing a business letter, making a presentation, or taking part in a role-playing conversation are a few examples of these kinds of assignments. Students can exhibit their language proficiency in a more genuine and meaningful way and get pertinent, useful feedback by using these kinds of tests.

DISCUSSION

Alternative techniques to assessment and evaluation are required, as indicated by the findings of the analysis of previous studies on these topics in language textbooks for non-philological subjects. The existing approaches in language textbooks for non-philological subjects can result in a lack of authenticity, reliability, and validity in the assessment process and are

frequently limited in their capacity to effectively evaluate students' language skills and abilities. Self-assessment, peer assessment, and project-based assessment are three different strategies that can help students overcome these constraints and give them more genuine, trustworthy, and legitimate assessment and evaluation experiences. These methods can be modified to fit the needs of children in a range of situations and have been demonstrated to be successful in fostering student learning and growth.

CONCLUSION

In order to better serve the needs of both teachers and students, the assessment and evaluation techniques employed in language textbooks for non-philological subjects need to be updated. Other methods, such project-based assessment, peer assessment, and self-assessment, can give students more genuine, trustworthy, and legitimate assessment and evaluation experiences. Students can acquire the language proficiency required to be successful in their chosen field by integrating these alternate methods into language textbooks for non-philological subjects.

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